

Intelligent Prepaid Energy Meter

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Abstract

Energy is a vital resource for any developing nation, and the amount of energy consumed is closely linked to the country's economic growth. Unfortunately, energy theft is a global issue, not just limited to India, with losses estimated at around \$96 billion annually. This results in significant financial losses for energy-producing companies. In addition, some consumers intentionally delay bill payments, which disrupts cash flow and creates operational challenges for utility providers. To address these issues, we propose an innovative solution in the form of an intelligent prepaid energy meter. This meter accurately measures the energy consumed by the user, offers a prepaid recharge option to prevent payment delays, and incorporates a tamper detection system to curb energy theft. Furthermore, the smart meter includes a remote switch control feature, allowing users to remotely manage the ON/OFF status of household appliances. This integrated approach ensures more efficient energy usage, enhances security, and helps improve cash flow management for energy providers.

Keywords: Prepaid, Power Theft, Remote Monitoring, Raspberry Pi, Bidirectional Energy Meter, Arduino Nano, RS-485.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Electrical energy theft is a criminal activity where individuals illegally tap into electrical lines or manipulate energy meters to reduce their utility bills”. Electricity theft not only undermines the revenue of energy-producing companies but also poses serious safety risks. Tampering with energy meters can lead to hazardous conditions, such as fire risks from short circuits or overcurrent situations. Additionally, it can cause electric shocks to individuals who attempt to steal power or even innocent bystanders near the affected equipment. Detecting energy theft is a significant challenge for utility companies, often compounded by corruption, where bribed personnel fail to report instances of theft. This unreported loss, categorized as non-technical loss, is ultimately passed on to consumers through higher tariff rates, resulting in unfair costs for law-abiding users.

To combat this issue, our solution focuses on preventing energy theft through continuous monitoring of voltage and current at the energy meter's input and the circuit board, forming a closed-loop system. The Raspberry Pi Zero W module is used to compare these voltage and current values in real time. Consumers can also track their electricity usage via a smartphone app, ensuring better awareness of their consumption patterns.

Moreover, remote access is provided through an Arduino nano, allowing users to control the ON/OFF status of the loads connected to the system. The meter incorporates a prepaid recharge feature, and once the units are depleted, the power supply is automatically cut off. Both the consumer and service provider receive an instant alert when the power is disconnected, ensuring prompt action is taken. This

integrated solution not only prevents energy theft but also enhances the efficiency of power usage, providing more control and transparency for both consumers and utility providers.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Power theft is a significant concern in India, leading to substantial financial losses for power generation companies and severe power quality issues. Approximately 20-30% of transmission and distribution (T&D) losses in certain regions result from unauthorized tampering with power lines. This issue is prevalent across industrial, commercial, and domestic sectors, severely impacting the efficiency of the electricity grid. Beyond monetary losses, power theft also poses serious safety hazards, including electrical fires, shocks, and damage to appliances and equipment. To address this challenge, the Electricity Act of 2003 was enacted, criminalizing power theft and imposing heavy fines and imprisonment for offenders. However, despite these regulations, the theft rate remains high due to corruption, bribery, and negligence in enforcement. To combat this, we propose an Intelligent Prepaid Energy Meter equipped with Raspberry Pi, Arduino Uno, and a PZEM module to detect tampering and ensure timely bill payments. The system allows consumers to monitor real-time energy consumption through the Thing Speak cloud platform and provides a prepaid recharge facility to prevent overdue payments. Additionally, users can remotely control their electrical appliances via a smartphone-based ON/OFF switch, enhancing convenience, security, and efficient energy usage.

3. OBJECTIVES

The objective of the proposed project, "Intelligent Prepaid Energy Meter," is to enhance security and streamline billing by preventing unauthorized tampering with energy meters, such as meter bypassing, double feeding, and tapping into power lines. Additionally, the system aims to eliminate delays in bill payments by implementing a prepaid system, ensuring timely payments and reducing the risk of fraud and energy theft.

- 1) Preventing Energy Theft and unauthorized Access to Energy Meter.
- 2) Automated Recharge and Balance Management.
- 3) Real time Monitoring and Alerts.
- 4) Remote Control Over Home Appliances

4. LITERATURE SURVEY

D. Harshitha Reddy, P. Shilpa "Intelligent Prepaid Energy Meter for the design and implementation of an Arduino – based prepaid energy meter using GSM technology." Published in 2017 1st International Conference on next generation Computing Technologies (IEEE-2017). This paper termed as intelligent prepaid energy meter because it reads energy consumption, automatically detects power theft and disconnects the power supply when total units are equal to zero without any human supervision. Traditional postpaid energy meters require manual reading, billing, and payment, often leading to inefficiencies such as delayed payments and power theft. Intelligent prepaid energy meters offer a pay-before-use model, reducing revenue losses for utility providers and giving consumers better control over their energy usage. With the advancement in smart grid technology, intelligent prepaid energy meters have gained significant attention. These meters provide efficient energy management, real-time monitoring, and prepaid billing systems, reducing power theft and human intervention. This literature survey explores various methodologies, technologies, and advancements in intelligent prepaid energy meters. Microcontroller- based Prepaid meters Research by Sharma et al. (2018) explored the use of Arduino and PIC microcontrollers to develop prepaid meters with RFID-based recharge systems. GSM & IoT-Based Prepaid Meters Gupta et al. (2019) proposed a GSM-based prepaid energy meter that allows users to recharge via mobile networks. IoT-based solutions such as MQTT and cloud platforms are also integrated for real-time monitoring. Smart metering technologies enabled real-time monitoring, automated meter reading, and remote disconnect/reconnect capabilities. The integration of IoT and wireless communication technologies has enabled IPEMs to communicate with users, utilities, and other smart devices.

5. CONCEPT AND METHODOLOGY

A. Block Diagram

Fig. Intelligent Prepaid Energy Meter Block Diagram

B. Working of system

The system monitors energy consumption using a MODBUS energy meter, which is connected to a Raspberry Pi. The Raspberry Pi transmits the data to the 'ThingSpeak' cloud server for real-time monitoring. Key parameters measured include energy consumption, power factor, frequency, power, current, and voltage.

To detect potential power theft, the system incorporates two Miniature Circuit Breakers (MCB) configured in series and parallel. The series-connected MCB handles the normal AC main supply, while the parallel MCB is used to simulate power theft in the system. This configuration helps in distributing power to multiple loads while safeguarding the wiring in a household.

The system consists of two primary modules:

1. Smart Energy Meter Module: This module displays the power consumption on both the energy meter's screen and the smartphone via the 'ThingSpeak' cloud server.
2. Power Distribution Module: This is an add-on module responsible for detecting power theft, disconnecting power when the prepaid balance is depleted, and providing remote control over the switches using an Arduino Nano.

Operation Flow:

- When the series-connected MCB is engaged, the system operates normally, with no theft detected, and power is supplied to the loads.
- When the parallel MCB is turned on, the system identifies a discrepancy between the energy meter's readings and the load values, triggering a power theft alert.
- If the prepaid balance falls below a defined threshold, the system generates a low balance alert. When the total energy units are depleted (i.e., the balance reaches zero), the system automatically disconnects the power supply to the loads via relays.

This setup ensures the efficient monitoring of energy usage, prevents unauthorized power usage, and offers remote control for enhanced system management.

6. COMPONENTS

1. Modbus Energy Meter (EM)
2. Power Distribution Module (PDM)
3. 4 Channel Relay Module
4. AC Power Measurement Module (PZEM-04T)
5. Arduino Nano
6. ACS712 Current Sensor
7. TTL To RS485 Module
8. Intelligent Prepaid Energy Meter (IPEM)
9. Raspberry Pi Zero W (R-Pi)
10. Power Supply (12V SMPS Adapter)
11. USB To RS485 Module
12. 12V Battery Pack
13. Miscellaneous Electronic / Electrical Components

RESULTS

In this study, a sophisticated prepaid energy meter system is developed, capable of accurately measuring and monitoring various electrical parameters, including total energy consumption, voltage, current, power factor, and other essential metrics. The primary objective of the system is to integrate real-time monitoring capabilities with prepaid energy metering, thereby improving energy management and operational efficiency.

Measurement and Comparison with Smart Energy Meters:

To ensure the proper functioning of the intelligent prepaid energy meter and confirm that it operates within expected parameters, data from both meters are transmitted to the ThingSpeak cloud platform. Both the intelligent prepaid energy meter and the smart energy meter's readings are compared and displayed on the platform, providing an opportunity to assess whether the measurements align within acceptable error margins. The successful correlation of data from both meters confirms the reliability and accuracy of the proposed system.

Fig. Connection and Wiring of the Intelligent Prepaid Energy Meter

Automated Low-Value Alert and Load Disconnection:

A key feature of the proposed system is its ability to automatically detect zero energy consumption. When the total energy consumption drops to zero, indicating that the connected load has either been turned off or is malfunctioning, the system generates an immediate low-value alert within 10 seconds. This ensures that users are promptly notified of abnormal consumption patterns, such as a system fault or an inactive load. Once this low-value alert is triggered, the system automatically disconnects the load to prevent unnecessary energy wastage or potential damage. This automated action eliminates the need for manual intervention, ensuring more efficient and safe energy management. This functionality is particularly beneficial in scenarios where human oversight may be absent, or where immediate corrective action is required to prevent energy inefficiencies.

Sr. No.	Operations	Time
1.	Tripping Operation when balance is Zero.	0.2sec
2.	Tripping when theft is detected	0.1sec
3.	Operation when switches are turn ON/OFF from Mobile	0.1sec

Table :- Time taken by the system for Switching operations

CONCLUSION

The central component of our proposed system consists of a Raspberry Pi integrated with a smart energy meter, working in tandem to monitor and display real-time energy consumption data. This system provides immediate visibility of energy usage, with the data being accessible not only through the meter’s built-in screen but also on users' smartphones. This dual-mode display significantly enhances user awareness of their energy consumption, thereby fostering more informed decision-making and encouraging energy conservation.

In addition to the Raspberry Pi, the system incorporates a PZEM module and an Arduino Nano, which are pivotal in detecting power theft. The system establishes a closed-loop connection between the energy meter and the distribution board, ensuring that any discrepancies in energy consumption are promptly identified.

Moreover, the system supports remote control functionality for home appliances, empowering users to manage their electrical devices from any location. This feature allows for real-time monitoring and remote operation, facilitating more efficient energy utilization. Ultimately, the system plays a crucial role in optimizing energy use, providing greater convenience, and supporting sustainable energy practices.

FUTURE SCOPE

In the future, our project can be further enhanced by integrating advanced technologies to better meet consumer expectations and improve overall system performance:

- **Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning:** These technologies can be employed for predictive analytics and intelligent theft detection. By analysing historical consumption patterns, AI and ML algorithms could forecast future energy usage, helping consumers optimize their consumption habits. Additionally, AI-driven anomaly detection models could identify unusual behaviour indicative of power theft, enabling faster and more accurate responses.
- **Blockchain Technology:** The incorporation of blockchain can ensure secure and transparent bill transactions.
- **Integration with IoT Technology:** Expanding the system's connectivity with Internet of Things devices would allow for broader automation and smarter energy management.
- **Wireless Communication with PZEM Modules and Wi-Fi:** To increase the system's flexibility and reduce the need for complex wiring, wireless PZEM modules and Wi-Fi communications could be integrated into the setup

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